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Review Article

A Review On Preparation Of Herbal Shampoo, Uses And Products Available In Market

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ABSTRACT

As we know that the hairs are an integral part of the human beauty which is protective appendages of the body integument with sebaceous glands and sweat glands. To maintain the growth and integrity of hair we have to clean the hair and scalp daily for proper development. For this we use various types of shampoos like herbal shampoo, anti-dandruff shampoo, conditioning shampoo etc. shampoo is nothing but preparation of surfactant with the combination of active ingredient in the form of powder, liquid, semisolid solution to clean, beautify, condition the scalp by removing dirt, dust, unwanted particles without affecting scalp, hair. In this article we are going to review about preparation method of herbal shampoo, need of herbal shampoo, Various uses of herbal shampoo and products which are available in the market.

INTRODUCTION

A shampoo is defined as a preparation of a Surface Active agent in the form of liquid, solid, or powder which are used under the conditions specified to remove surface grease, dirt, and skin debris from the hair, shaft, and scalp without adversely affecting the hair, scalp or the health of the user.(1) Shampoos are widely used cosmetic products for cleaning and beautifying hair which also changes the hair texture and provides nutrients to it beautiful.(2) now many chemical, and synthetic

shampoos are available in the market but they also have so many side like hair loss problems and hair damage, so to avoid these damages many consumers use herbal shampoos. (3) Herbal shampoos contains plant-based ingredients in the form of botanical extracts, essential oils, and other organic compounds instead of their conventional counterparts.(4) The use of shampoo is to remove the undesirable dirt, dust increased in between the hair without stripping out and Cleaning the

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hair.(5)The basic idea of hair growth enhancing & conditioning shampoo is lies in the Rigveda, Yajurveda, Ayurveda, Unani, and Homeopathic systems of medicine where these are the products in which herb is used in crude or extract form. (6) Hair is also known as epidermal derivative as they are originated from the epidermis during embryological development. It is an appendage on the body, integument with sebaceous glands, sweat glands, and nails derived from the skin ectoderm. (7) Hair is a protein filament grows from follicles found in the dermis, or skin which define the characteristics of mammals. To increase the hair integrity products which increase hair volume, reduce frizz, improve hair manageability, and stimulate new hair growth must be used. (8)

Need of Shampoo:

A shampoo is a solution of a detergent with suitable additives for hair conditioning, lubrication, medication which are safe and free from side effects. (9) Ravichandran et.al (2004) reported the clinical efficacy and safety of “Herbal Antidandruff Shampoo’ in the management of dandruff. A polyherbal shampoo containing the extracts of Rosmarinus officinalis, Vetiverla zizanioides, Nigella sativa, Santalum album, Ficus bengalensis, Citrus limon, and oil of Melaleuca leucadendron was used in the study. Which conclude that the test formulation is effective due to the synergistic anti-fungal, anti-inflammatory, and local immunostimulatory actions of its ingredients. (10)

Types of Herbal Shampoo:

A. Based on appearance.

- a. Powder shampoo
- b. Liquid shampoo or lotion shampoo
- c. Gel shampoo or Solid shampoo
- d. Cream shampoo
- e. Oil shampoo
- f. Miscellaneous anti-dandruff shampoo or medicated shampoo

B. Based on use or function

- a. Conditioning shampoo
- b. Antidandruff shampoo
- c. Baby shampoo
- d. Balancing shampoo
- e. Clarifying shampoo

C. Based on origin

- a. Herbal shampoo
- b. Egg shampoo (11)

Ideal Properties of Herbal Shampoo:

- i. It should be easily removed on rinsing with water.
- ii. It should not make the hand rough and chapped.
- iii. It should not cause any side effects/irritation to the skin or eye.
- iv. It should leave the hair non-dry, soft, lustrous with good manageability and minimum fly-away
- v. It should produce a good amount of foam to satisfy the psychological requirements of the user.
- vi. It should effectively and completely remove dust or soil, excessive sebum or other fatty substances, and loose corneal cells from the hair. (12)

Uses of Herbal Shampoo:

- i. Herbal shampoo contains All-natural, pure components in the formulation.
- ii. Herbal shampoo must have less/Absence of adverse effects
- iii. When herbal shampoo is used it gives More Shine to the hair.
- iv. Produce Less Hair Loss
- v. They can induce Long Lasting Colour
- vi. Herbal shampoo makes hair Stronger and More Fortified.
- vii. In herbal shampoo all components used are derived from Natural products, plants and materials with less/No use of Chemicals.
- viii. They Won't Irritate the Skin or Scalp
- ix. Skin-Friendly
- x. Eco-Friendly

- xi. They are Cost-Effective, Eco- friendly, skin-friendly with cleansing properties.
- xii. They mainly give treatment to the scalp to condition.
- xiii. they Relieves Itch and Irritation and repair damaged hairs. (13)

Steps involved in Preparation of Shampoo:

1. Collect, authenticate the herbal plant material which is going to used as key material.
2. Clean, Dry, grind the plant and accurately weigh the required amount of plant powdered using digital weighing balance.
3. Make a solution of powdered extract by maceration or other extraction methods, add a thickening agent if required and mix the solution properly.
4. Shake continuously at a time interval of 20min for better mixing of ingredients in the solution.
5. Heat the solution properly by heating mental in a container and add sufficient quantity of cleansing agent which maintain the pH balance and used for cleaning purpose.
6. Add few drops of aromatic agents/ aroma using dropper to impart few plaseant fragrance to the sample solution.
7. Add preservative to increase the stability and half life of the prepared herbal shampoo.
8. Then lastly check the pH level of prepared shampoo and adjust the pH with suitable pH buffer.
9. Then lastly perform various evaluation tests of prepared shampoo for its quality, stability, pH effectiveness. (14)

Products available in Market:

In India there are various synthetic and non-synthetic hair shampoos are available in market to clean, remove dirt, dust and improve hair growth, decrease hair loss. Here we are going to review few of herbal shampoos which are available in the market which reduce hair loss, prevent infection to

scalp, cleans the scalp, improve hair growth, stimulate hair growth, remove dirt and dust etc.

- a. RIVONA ALOE VERA SHAMPOO
- b. DABUR VATIKA SHAMPOO
- c. HIMALAYA NATURAL PROTEIN SHAMPOO
- d. KHADI MAURI HERBAL SHAMPOO
- e. SESA HAIR FALL CONTROL SHAMPOO
- f. LOTUS HERBAL SHAMPOO
- g. HERBAL ESSENCES
- h. BIOTIQUE OCEAN KELP ANTI HAIRFALL SHAMPOO
- i. VAADI HERBAL AMLA_SHIKAKAI SHAMPOO
- j. INDULEKHA BRINGHA HAIR CLEANSER

1. Rivona Aloe Vera Shampoo-

Rivona Naturals Aloe Vera Shampoo is Enriched with The Goodness of Aloe Vera, Known for Its Hydrating and Moisturizing Properties, Cleanses the Scalp tested dermatologically for Cruelty-Free, Paraben Free, Silicone Free, Phthalate Free, pH Balanced, No Harmful Chemicals. Rivona's aloe vera shampoo is 99% pure Aloe Vera, neem extracts that are enriched with several skin and hair care benefits. No artificial colour was added into it. IFRA-certified fragrance that is skin and hair-friendly ,Aloe Vera 90% Pure Extract and it Soothes and moisturizes the scalp, reduces dandruff, and promotes healthy hair growth. (15)

2. Dabur Vatika Shampoo –

Dabur Vatika is one of the trustworthy brands in India. The shampoo contains extracts of seven natural ingredients – henna, amla, shikakai, almond, hibiscus, reetha, and olive. It cleanses your hair scalp and conditions the hair, making it smoother, softer, and silkier. The shampoo has anti-dandruff properties and keeps the hair nourished all day long. It is also claimed to improve blood circulation, resulting in improved health of your hair and scalp. (16)

3. Himalaya Natural Protein Shampoo –

It is the herbal natural protein shampoo helps to strengthen the hair roots and minimize hair fall and damage. The product also moisturizes the hair and helps to retain its moisture. Enriched with natural extracts of chickpea, amla, licorice, henna, etc., it provides gentle care for your hair and keeps it manageable. The key ingredients of this products are nothing but Bhringaraja, Palash, Soya and Wheat. Chickpea is an excellent source of protein which nourishes hair, keep soft and smooth. Liquorice is used to moisturize the hair while proteins of Soy and Wheat helps to strengthen hair and reduce hair breakage, hair damage, smoothening, and nourishes the hair. (17)

4. Khadi Mauri Herbal shampoo –

The amla and bring raj extracts in Mauri Herbal Shampoo helps to strengthen the hair roots, prevent hair loss, and promote healthy hair growth. It also helps to remove dandruff and makes the hair shinier and silkier. The product is free from parabens and other harmful chemicals. The Gramodyog-certified Khadi product is suitable for every hair type. Khadi Aloe Vera shampoo is an anti-hair fall shampoo that provides hydration to your hair, keeps them pollutant-free, and makes your hair soft and silky. It has ayurvedic hair treatment properties and is made from natural extracts. It has a pleasant herbal fragrance and is pale green with a silvery sheen on it. The shampoo lathers well and makes your scalp squeaky clean. It is the best Khadi shampoo for dandruff reduction. Aloe Vera, Amla, Reetha, Jatamanasi, Bringraj, Heena, Tulsi, Shikakai, Brahmi, Neem, Godhra are the key ingredients of this shampoo which Cures dry and itchy scalp, SLS and paraben-free, Effective scalp cleanser, Conditions hair, Removes flakiness and dandruff, Repairs damaged hair, Makes your hair frizz-free and silky, Lathers up easily Some notes for using this shampoo: requires a conditioner if you have extremely dry hair, Takes time to show effective results. (18)

5. Sesa Hair Fall Control Shampoo –

The Sesa Ayurvedic Medicinal Hair Fall Control Shampoo is a product specifically designed to address hair fall issues, promote healthy hair growth formulated with a unique blend of 17 nourishing herbs that work together to control hair fall, boost hair growth, and prevent bacterial and fungal infections on the scalp. With regular use, this shampoo can help in reducing hair shedding. Sesa Hair Shampoo also promotes the growth of healthier and fuller hair. This hair fall control shampoo nourishes and strengthens the hair, preventing premature greying Sesa Ayurvedic shampoo is made with 100% natural ingredients and is free from parabens, making it safe and gentle for all hair types. (19)

6. Lotus Herbal Shampoo –

An Ayurvedic Lotus shampoo is composed of shikakai, amla, behra, reetha suitable for any hair type used to remove impurities and pollutants from the scalp and helps to strengthen the hair. The shampoo also contains Triphala which helps in reducing hair fall and maintains the scalp's natural pH. The shampoo also gives a lustrous shine to your hair. This Formulated Shampoo is impregnated with Soya & Brahmi Extracts that keep hair soft, thick, and black. (20)

7. Herbal Essences –

Herbal Essence shampoo is made from 90% naturally acquired ingredients. If your hair is weakened and it consumes the dirt and germs throughout the day then bio renews natural antioxidants remove impurities to protect your hair from damage: purified water and natural-source ingredient materials with limited processing. All the ingredients present in the shampoo are good for color-treated hair. It protects the hair from damage and discoloration. The bio renew collections are a unique (21)

8. Biotique Ocean Kelp Anti-Hairfall Shampoo –

Biotique shampoo cleanses hair and reduces hair fall to a great extent. It contains kelp, natural

proteins, peppermint oil, and mint leaf extracts that penetrate deep into the layers and invigorate the scalp for fresh growth and a healthier shine. Prominent Features of the Biotique Ocean Kelp Anti Hairfall Shampoo is that it is enriched with proteins that prevent hair fall and eliminate it in the long run which is formulated with pure kelp, it promotes healthy hair growth at a faster pace. (22)

9. Vaadi Herbal Amla Shikakai Shampoo –

It is enriched with the goodness of amla, shikakai, and reetha. It shows triple-action plan which promote a healthy scalp, strengthening hair roots, and deep conditioning to the hair. It reduces hair fall, the natural extracts clean and nourish the hair without harming the hair follicles. The shampoo is free from any harmful chemical ingredients with the excellent combination of herbs like Amla, Shikakai and Reetha and free from SLS. (23)

10. Indulekha Bringha Hair Cleanser-

Indulekha Bringha Shampoo is a proprietary Ayurvedic medicine to reduce the hair fall made with 6 herbs and essential oil making it even more potent. Apart from Bringharaj, it also contains herbs like Neem, Shikakai, Tulsi, and Amla which are known to provide rich source of antioxidants, minerals, micronutrients, and vitamins. The presence of these minerals and nutrients helps in reducing hair fall, increases blood circulation to the scalp, and strengthens hair follicles. Further, the presence of micronutrients helps in the effective cleansing of the scalp caused by dirt and pollution. (24)

CONCLUSION:

Hair is an integral part of human beauty and protective appendages we have to maintain the growth, health and integrity of hairs. For maintenance of integrity, we have to clean the hair and maintain growth daily for this shampoo is one of the products used to integrate the growth. As we already know in market there are number of synthetic shampoos are available but they also have various side effects and as in ayurveda we use

various herbal plants for various diseases or disorders we can also use these herbal plants for maintaining the hair integrity in the form of herbal shampoos. Herbal shampoos are nothing but the medicinal products prepared from herbal plant or part of plant as active ingredient with other additives in the form of solid, liquid or semi-solid form to clean, beautify, induce growth, reduce hair fall and maintain the integrity of the hairs. In this article we reviewed some of the points like herbal shampoos, the various types of herbal shampoos on the basis of function, on the basis of appearance and on the basis of origin and also studied their uses like cleaning, maintaining hair growth, reduce hair fall, acts as anti-dandruff, anti-fungal, anti-bacterial etc., we also reviewed the process of preparation of herbal shampoo and some off marketed herbal products like Rivona hair shampoo moisturizes the hair, Vatika shampoo acts as anti-dandruff, Himalaya hair shampoo strengthens the hair roots and reduce damages of hairs, Sesa shampoo reduce hair fall, lotus herbal shampoo reduce hair fall and maintain the pH of scalp, herbal essences reduce discoloration of hair, biotique shampoo acts as anti-hair fall and Indulekha Bringha hair cleanser reduce hair fall and increase blood circulation.

REFERENCES:

1. Ashok Kumar and Rakesh Roshan Mali, EVALUATION OF PREPARED SHAMPOO FORMULATIONS AND TO COMPARE FORMULATED SHAMPOO WITH MARKETED SHAMPOOS, Volume 3, Issue 1, July – August 2010; Article 025 ISSN 0976 – 044x
2. Janrao Kaveri, Gaikwad Vishal Shivaji //A REVIEW ON HERBAL SHAMPOO>> Volume 10, Issue 10 October 2022 | ISSN: 2320-2882.
3. Yogesh B. Raut, Sanjay K. Bais, Shweta Badure Fabtech College of Pharmacy, Sangola, A REVIEW: AN ANALYSIS AND

- FORMULATION OF THE HERBAL SHAMPOO, *International Journal of Pharmacy and Herbal Technology*- ISSN NO: 2583-8962, Vol.1 (3) Oct-Dec. 2023: 132-140.
4. E.Bartkutė. Master's thesis "Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Shampoo"/ thesis supervisor Prof. Jurga Bernatoniė; Lithuanian University of Health Sciences, Medical Academy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Institute of Pharmaceutical Technologies. - Kaunas.
 5. Dhayanithi S, Enjamamul HOQUE, Pallavi N, Dr. Kavitha PN, and Dr. Saraswathi: Formulation and evaluation of herbal shampoo >>National Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences 2021; 1(2): 88-93E-ISSN: 2788-9270 /P-ISSN: 2788-9262/NJPS 2021; 1(2): 88-93/Received: 03-06-2021/Accepted: 07-07-2021.
 6. Namita¹, Nimisha*¹/ Formulation, And Evaluation of Herbal Shampoo Having Antimicrobial Potential >>ISSN- 0975-1491 Vol 5, Suppl 3, 2013.
 7. HERBAL SHAMPOO: A REVIEW by Mr. Barde Gaurav S *¹., Prof. Mali Shubhangi R*². Mr. Barde Gaurav S *¹., Prof. Mali Shubhangi R*². *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Vol 3, Issue 6, pp 74-81, June 2022.
 8. HERBAL SHAMPOO: A REVIEW by Mr. Barde Gaurav S *¹., Prof. Mali Shubhangi R*². Mr. Barde Gaurav S *¹., Prof. Mali Shubhangi R*². *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Vol 3, Issue 6, pp 74-81, June 2022.
 9. Janrao Kaveri, Gaikwad Vishal Shivaji //A REVIEW ON HERBAL SHAMPOO>> Volume 10, Issue 10 October 2022 | ISSN: 2320-2882
 10. Pooja Arora,¹ Dr. Arun Nanda², Dr. Maninder Karan³, SHAMPOOS BASED ON SYNTHETIC INGREDIENTS VIS-À-VIS SHAMPOOS BASED ON HERBAL INGREDIENTS: A REVIEW, Volume 7, Issue 1, March – April 2011; Article-007 ISSN 0976 – 044X
 11. A REVIEW ON HERBAL SHAMPOO Disha A. Deulkar*, Pooja R. Hatwar, R. L. Bakal, N. B. Kohale and J. A. Kubde Department of Pharmaceutics, Shri Swami Samarth Institute of Pharmacy, At Parsodi, Dhamangaon Rly-444709 Maharashtra, India Volume 12, Issue 22, 265-277. ISSN 2277–7105 DOI: 10.20959/wjpr202322-30502.
 12. HERBAL SHAMPOO: A REVIEW by Mr. Barde Gaurav S *¹., Prof. Mali Shubhangi R*². Mr. Barde Gaurav S *¹., Prof. Mali Shubhangi R*². *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Vol 3, Issue 6, pp 74-81, June 2022.
 13. FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL SHAMPOO by Suyog Sunil Bhagwat Dr. N. J. Paulbudhe College of Pharmacy, Ahmednagar 414003. Maharashtra © 2020 IJCRT | Volume 8, Issue 9 September 2020 | ISSN: 2320-2882
 14. FORMULATION, EVALUATION, AND COMPARISON OF THE HERBAL SHAMPOO WITH THE COMMERCIAL SHAMPOOS by Khaloud Al Badi, Shah A. Khan*Department of Pharmacy, Oman Medical College, Muscat, Oman
 15. Marketed By: Rivona Herbal LLP Grandeur Building, 4th floor, Veera Desai Road, Andheri(W), Mumbai -400053 Manufactured by Spatz Cosmeceutical Inc. Plot no.8,9,10 Satellite industrial Estate, Kathwada,Ahmedabad, Gujarat -382430 INDIA <https://rivona.in/products/pure-aloe-vera-shampoo?srsId=AfmBOoo9OoOpUQNF7F-zdHh8GrIOZnaraOhlqxpIn7g9gHJ-89zaxuyt>
 16. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370224456_Formulation_and_Evaluations_of_Her

